

A New Synthesis of 5-Phenyl(methyl)-2,3,8-trisubstituted-imidazo[1,2-d]-as-triazines

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2-Aroyl-4,5-disubstituted-imidazoles prepared from diketones (benzil and furil) and phenacylaldehydes were acylated in THF medium at the N₁-site to afford the 1-acyl-2-aryol-4,5-disubstituted-imidazoles (3). Cyclocondensation of 3 with hydrazine hydrate afforded the title compounds in appreciable yield.

VARIOUS derivatives of imidazo-*as*-triazines are found to possess diverse pharmacological activities¹. In continuation of our programme directed for the development of new procedures for the synthesis of bridgehead nitrogen heterocycles, we report here a novel and efficient synthesis of 5-phenyl(methyl)-2,3,8-trisubstituted-imidazo[1,2-*d*]-*as*-triazines starting from diketones.

We started from 2-aryol-4,5-disubstituted-imidazoles, which in turn were prepared from diketones like benzil and furil. Heating an intimate mixture of a diketone and phenacyl aldehyde² in acetic acid with excess ammonium acetate afforded the desired compound (2) according to the method of Steck and Day³. These aroylimidazoles are coloured crystalline compounds with definite melting points. The ir spectra (CHCl₃) of all these compounds exhibited well-defined peaks around 3 300 (NH), 1 700 (C=O) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C-N). Our initial efforts in the acylation of the N₁-site of the imidazole nucleus with conventional reagents like pyridine-Ac₂O⁴ and pyridine-acetyl chloride⁵ were met with failure. It was presumed that the acidic imidazole hydrogen was not available in the basic medium. We therefore explored the possible use of Staab's procedure⁶ for the acylation reaction. All the 2-aryolimidazoles were allowed to react with acetyl chloride or benzoyl chloride (2 : 1 molar ratio) at room temperature in THF medium. After filtering off the resulting precipitate of imidazolium chloride, the 2-aryol-4,5-disubstituted-azolides (3) of good purity were obtained by simply evaporating the solvents under reduced pressure. The structure of these compounds were confirmed by elemental analyses and spectral data. The ir spectra of 3 exhibited sharp peaks around 1 695, 1 685, 1 610 and 1 500 cm⁻¹ for two C=O, C=N and C-N groups, respectively. Further, as expected, the NH peak at 3 300 cm⁻¹ was absent confirming that the N₁-site of the imidazole has undergone facile substitution by an acyl substituent.

All the imidazoles (3) with 1,4-dicarbonyl functions are the key synthetic intermediates for the

subsequent reactions with hydrazine hydrate in absolute ethanol to furnish the imidazo[1,2-*d*]-*as*-triazines (4) (Scheme 1). The structure of 4 was

a ; R=Ar=C₆H₅
b ; R=C₆H₅, Ar=*p*-ClC₆H₄
c ; R=2-furyl, Ar=C₆H₅
d ; R=2-furyl, Ar=*p*-ClC₆H₄
R=C₆H₅, 2-furyl
R¹=CH₃, C₆H₅
Ar=C₆H₅, *p*-ClC₆H₄

Scheme 1

confirmed by elemental analysis and spectral data. The ir spectra (CHCl₃) showed intense peaks at 1 605 and 1 615 cm⁻¹ assignable to C=N groups. Additionally, carbonyl absorption peaks at 1 695 and 1 685 cm⁻¹ present in their precursors (3), were absent indicating thereby that facile cyclisation occurred.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-AROYL-4,5-DISUBSTITUTED-IMIDAZOLES (2)*

Compd. no.	R	Ar	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	N % : Found/(Calcd.)
2a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	77	137–38	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	8.68 (8.64)
2b	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	59	195	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ N ₂ OCl	7.75 (7.82)
2c	Furyl	C ₆ H ₅	78	219–20	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	9.30 (9.21)
2d	Furyl	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	74	175–76	C ₁₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	8.08 (8.28)

*All compounds furnished satisfactory C and H analyses.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-AROYL-4,5-DISUBSTITUTED-1-ACYLIMIDAZOLES (3)

Compd. no.	R	R'	Ar	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
							C	H	N
3a	C ₆ H ₅	OH ₂	C ₆ H ₅	87	176	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	78.58 (78.68)	4.93 (4.91)	7.56 (7.65)
3b	C ₆ H ₅	OH ₂	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	45	243	C ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	71.89 (72.00)	4.18 (4.25)	7.05 (7.00)
3c	Furyl	OH ₂	C ₆ H ₅	52	239–40	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂	69.37 (69.36)	4.12 (4.04)	8.05 (8.09)
3d	Furyl	OH ₂	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	40	221	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	62.93 (63.10)	3.40 (3.44)	7.28 (7.36)
3e	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	73	231–32	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	81.22 (81.30)	4.73 (4.67)	6.51 (6.54)
3f	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	39	254–55	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	75.15 (75.30)	4.16 (4.12)	6.01 (6.06)
3g	Furyl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	83	208	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	73.47 (73.52)	3.86 (3.92)	6.71 (6.86)
3h	Furyl	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	42	232–34	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	67.60 (67.87)	3.42 (3.39)	6.28 (6.33)

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF IMIDAZO[1,2-*d*]-2S-TRIAZINES (4)*

Compd. no.	R	R'	Ar	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	N % : Found/(Calcd.)
4a	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	69	199–200	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄	15.33 (15.46)
4b	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	45	220	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₄ Cl	14.04 (14.14)
4c	Furyl	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	49	258	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	16.47 (16.37)
4d	Furyl	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	64	236–37	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	14.82 (14.89)
4e	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	66	232	C ₂₉ H ₂₀ N ₄	13.31 (13.20)
4f	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	53	296–98	C ₂₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ Cl	12.02 (12.22)
4g	Furyl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	42	218	C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	13.88 (13.85)
4h	Furyl	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	41	247–48	C ₂₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	12.90 (12.78)

*All compounds furnished satisfactory C and H analyses.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrometer.

Phenacyl aldehydes were prepared² from phenacyl bromides: phenacyl aldehyde, m.p. 67° (lit.² 67°); *p*-chlorophenacyl aldehyde, m.p. 113–14° (lit.² 114°). Furiol was prepared following

the reported procedure², m.p. 164–66° (lit.² 165–66°).

2-Aroyl-4,5-disubstituted-imidazoles (2) from diketones. General procedure: To a mixture of 1,2-diketone (benzil or furil; 0.06 mol) and ammonium acetate (9.24 g, 0.12 mol) in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) was added phenacyl aldehyde (0.06 mol). The mixture was refluxed for 1 h, then cooled, poured into cold water (200 ml) and neutralised

with liquor ammonia. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ice-cold water, dried and recrystallisation from ethanol to give pure 2-aryl-4,5-disubstituted (phenyl or furyl) imidazoles (2; Table 1).

Acylation of 2-aryl-4,5-disubstituted-imidazoles (2). Isolation of imidazoles (3). General procedure: To a stirred solution of 2-aryl-4,5-disubstituted-imidazole (2; 0.005 mol) in THF (50 ml) was added acetyl chloride or benzoyl chloride (0.006 mol) and stirring continued for 5 h. The precipitated imidazolium chloride was filtered and the filtrate was carefully evaporated to half its volume. On cooling, the resulting compound 3 was filtered and recrystallised from benzene (Table 2).

Reaction of 3 with hydrazine hydrate. Isolation of imidazo[1,2-d]-as-triazines (4). General procedure: To a solution of 3 (0.007 mol) in hot absolute ethanol (100 ml) was added hydrazine hydrate (1 g, 0.02 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 4 h. After evaporation of the solvent to half its volume and cooling, the resulting triazine was filtered, dried and crystallised from benzene to yield the product 4 (Table 3).

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